

CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS: A MIXED-METHOD STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 8

Pages: 1336-1357

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2915

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14642008

Manuscript Accepted: 12-06-2024

Cultural Intelligence of Private School Teachers: A Mixed-Method Study

Wendilyn A. Balinon,* Kristy Jane R. Muegna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This mixed-methods study, employing a convergent parallel approach, investigated the cultural intelligence (CQ) of private school teachers in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, Philippines, it also focuses on their experiences in teaching diverse cultural students. The participants were private school teachers from all private schools in Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. For the quantitative study, 92 teachers were chosen using complete enumeration sampling, while 10 teachers were purposefully selected for in-depth interviews. The study revealed the high level of cultural intelligence among teachers in strategy, knowledge, motivation, and behavior. The result shows that teacher creates inclusive classrooms, overcome language barriers, manage conflicts arising from cultural differences, and address potential biases. They actively use cultural intelligence to adapt their teaching methods, build relationships with students, and foster an inclusive learning environment. Moreover, key challenges identified including language barriers, communication styles, and navigating cultural sensitivities. In connection, they also emphasized the importance of professional development to enhance their cultural intelligence through seminars and training. Finally, it shows that teachers demonstrate a high level of cultural intelligence and teachers are well-prepared to work with students from different backgrounds.

Keywords: *cultural intelligence, convergent parallel approach, private school teachers, Philippines*

Introduction

Since the world is getting flatter, the classroom is thought of as a mirror that frequently reflects this phenomenon on a microcosmic level. Teachers' responsibilities and roles have grown more complex as they continue to work with a student body that is becoming more and more culturally and linguistically diverse. This is because they must meet the needs of all students while also attending to the academic and institutional demands of their jobs. It is imperative that learning concepts be changed to support forms that stimulate engagement and behavioral responses. In order to implement the reforms, procedures and systems that allow all members of the community to be involved in students' and others' education are needed. It is necessary to change the educational process so that the general public can take part and make contributions (Rajaram, 2023).

In the international setting, especially those in the United States, confront obstacles in their pursuit of helping teachers in most colleges and institutions become more culturally intelligent. For the most part, American teacher preparation programs do not adequately incorporate cultural intelligence into their courses, despite the increased emphasis in higher education on internationalization and global intelligence. The preparation of children for a globally interconnected world necessitates the possession of cultural intelligence, which presents a problem for educators. Within their teacher preparation courses, teachers face a number of obstacles and difficulties in their pursuit of global education and experiences (Parkhouse et al., 2015).

In the Philippines, the issue of multicultural education, which is believed to have affected many other nations, is not sufficiently addressed by instructors in the Philippines. It is predicted that there will be occasions when teachers treat their pupils unfairly when it comes to subject matter, classroom discussions, cultural and religious education, and other things because of these various cultural, social, and religious orientations. In multicultural environments, it is inevitable that teachers will have to accept the diversity of each student. Teachers' ought to give cultural intelligence top priority since it could have an impact on their performance (Baron, 2021).

The urgency of the study lies in the growing importance of equipping private school teacher with cultural intelligence. In an increasingly interconnected world, where classrooms are becoming more diverse, it is imperative that teacher have a comprehensive training to understand, respect, and effectively communicate with individuals from various cultural backgrounds. Consequently, this study serves as a critical step towards ensuring that private school teachers are adequately prepared to navigate cultural boundaries and contribute to a more inclusive and globally aware educational landscape. Additionally, this study has a social relevance for the fact that the school is becoming more culturally diverse and the results of this research will benefit the schools, policymakers and communities. Furthermore, this study's insights can help in bridging cultural diversity within Kapalong community and foster a more inclusive and harmonious social environment.

There were various studies being conducted that are somewhat related to this study, such as the study of Didem (2020) that investigated "Cultural Intelligence Levels of Pre-Service Teachers," while Dagohoy (2018) explored "The Mediating Effect of Cultural Intelligence on the Relationship Between Leadership Practices and School Effectiveness." Furthermore, Puppo (2019) examined "Cross-Cultural Competence in Higher Education Faculty and Staff." The aforementioned studies are distinct from one another since the first investigates at pre-service teachers' cultural intelligence (CQ) levels and highlights how their levels vary depending on certain demographic factors. The second, discuss that cultural intelligence and leadership of school principals and teachers is always evident of positive school climate while the latter discussed cultural intelligence (CQ) and intercultural sensitivity in developing cultural

competence and adapt behavior for cultural commonality and difference to accomplish cross-cultural goals. However, this study, differs from the studies that I have discussed since this study will focus on how private school teachers build and use cultural intelligence in their academic and professional works.

This study explores the cultural intelligence of private school teachers as a means of bridging the gap between varied cultural backgrounds within the private school setting. The study seeks to clarify the cultural skills of educators. The commitment to community participation includes sharing the program's results with important stakeholders, including local community groups by sharing these results, it can adhere the value of cultural intelligence in learning environments and promote awareness, comprehension, and cooperation. The goal of this dissemination approach is to provide local communities and educational stakeholders with useful information so they may work together to create inclusive, culturally sensitive learning environments for all children.

Research Questions

This study investigated the exploration of cultural intelligence among private school teachers, by using the mixed methods research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to address the research problem at hand.

1. What is the status of cultural intelligence of private school teachers?
2. What are the lived experiences private school teacher with regards to their cultural intelligence in a diverse classroom?
3. What insights can teachers share regarding challenges faced in developing cultural intelligence during their professional academic work?
4. To what extent do the quantitative result corroborate with the qualitative result?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed methods strategy that links qualitative and quantitative components that give more explanation of the research subject that assert the legitimacy of mixed methods research depends on this integration, which can occur at any stage(s) of the research process. The term "mixing" refers to the act of fusing qualitative and quantitative elements to produce a more comprehensive description of the research topic (Halcomb & Hickman, 2015).

Combining two kinds of methods may be greater than utilizing only one since it is likely to reveal deep insights into the research phenomenon that cannot be fully comprehended by just either qualitative or quantitative approaches. A mixed-methods strategy integrates and combines multiple data sources to explore complicated problems. As mentioned in the section above, the use of MMR allows researchers to look at their topic from a broad perspective, allowing them to observe a phenomenon from a variety of research lenses and points of view (Shorten & Smith, 2017; Poth & Munce, 2020).

In context of this study the application of a mixed-methods approach is particularly advantageous. This approach allowed integration of both qualitative and quantitative data sources, enabled a more comprehensive examination of cultural intelligence among private school teachers. Given the complexity of the topic, it permits researchers to used mixed methods to gain a holistic understanding by examining the phenomenon through various perspectives and research lenses, ultimately offered rich insights that would be challenging to obtain using solely qualitative or quantitative approaches.

The convergent parallel design, also known as the convergent/triangulation design, is the simultaneous application of both quantitative and qualitative studies at the same stage of the research process. Both methodologies can make a major contribution to resolving the study subject because they are both given equal weight in this arrangement. This method preserves the research's objectivity throughout data collection and processing before combining or merging the findings throughout the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

Moreover, convergent design uses pragmatism as a theoretical foundation, it is a popular and successful method for combining approaches. This approach triangulates the data by combining quantitative and qualitative techniques. Prior to being independently analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative analytical methods, two distinct data sets are initially obtained concurrently. A researcher can completely understand the information provided by either the quantitative or qualitative outcomes alone in a convergent design by merging the two kinds of data (Creswell & Clark, 2018).

In context of my study the use the convergent parallel design is highly relevant. This research approach allows the simultaneous use of both quantitative and qualitative methods that examine cultural intelligence among private school teachers. By giving equal weight to both quantitative and qualitative data, this design ensures the comprehensive and objective exploration of the subject matter, preserving the integrity of the research process from data collection to final interpretation.

Respondents

Quantitative Phase

In this investigation, which conducted in the second semester of the school year. The respondents are private school teachers from

different private school in Kapalong, the Quezon Memorial Institute of Technology of Kapalong, Maryknoll High School of Maniki, Saint Jude Academy of Mindanao Foundation, Inc., Kapalong College of Technology Incorporated with a total of 92. They are chosen as respondents because the study focuses on the cultural intelligence of teachers working in a local private school in Kapalong.

Further, the respondents are determined through sampling, specifically, A method used in data analysis and surveys to look at every potential element in a finite set is complete enumeration sampling. In order to provide a representative sample based on predetermined criteria, it entails the selection, acquisition, and quantification of a portion within the population (Mizuno, 2023).

Lastly, this sampling method was particularly appropriate for this study because the respondents, who are private school teachers, were selected using complete enumeration. This method ensured that all potential participants were included in the sample, providing a comprehensive representation of the population of private school teachers in Kapalong.

Table 1.1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Private School</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
QMIS	27	27	29.35%
KCTI	23	23	25.00%
SJAMFI	17	17	18.48%
MHSM	25	25	27.17%
Total	92	92	100.00%

Qualitative Phase

The topics for a qualitative study, however, were specifically chosen. In this period, non-probability sampling, or purposeful sampling, was employed. The research questions were best addressed by participants who can also increase understanding of the topic under study (Kuper et al., 2008).

There are total of ten participants from the private school teachers; ten participants will be chosen for in-depth interviews. All of these individuals are working in private school in Kapalong. It is important to note that participants in the data collecting for the quantitative stages are not permitted to engage in the qualitative phase.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Private School</i>
IDI-01	Female	KCTI
IDI-02	Female	QMIS
IDI-03	Female	KCTI
IDI-04	Male	KCTI
IDI-05	Female	KCTI
IDI-06	Male	KCTI
IDI-07	Female	QMIS
IDI-08	Female	MHSM
IDI-09	Male	SJAMFI
IDI-10	Female	SJAMFI

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher used a cultural intelligence survey questionnaire that was adapted from Cultural Intelligence Center (2005). Psychometric features of the Cultural Intelligence Scale have been demonstrated to be satisfactory. The factor structure appears to be close to the hypothesized one, and reliability is very high (Cronbach's alpha in the first and second sessions was .94 and .95, respectively). Strategy, knowledge, motivation, and conduct were the indicators used in the aforementioned questionnaire, which employed a five-point Likert Scale.

Each question was rated on a five-point Likert scale by participants, who were instructed to mark one box on a scale from one (which represents the lowest rating) to five (which represents the highest rating) for each answer they felt best represented the question. The Likert Scale has been shown to be a good tool for evaluating concepts, viewpoints, and stimuli that are challenging for human senses to perceive. Despite being altered, the questionnaire received professional evaluation. In order to, investigate how people view organizational commitment we will provide a variety of instruments, justifications, and interpretations.

Qualitative Phase

As for the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was meticulously crafted by the researcher and underwent rigorous validation by a panel of experts. These questions were open-ended in nature and were carefully developed based on the findings from the previous survey phase. They served as a guiding compass for conducting in-depth interviews (IDIs). From the pool of participants who had completed the survey questionnaire in the preceding phase, a deliberate and purposive selection was made. Ten participants were chosen to participate in individual in-depth interviews (IDI). Interviews proved to be a valuable method for extracting

rich insights, personal narratives, experiences, diverse opinions, and other valuable information that cannot be adequately captured solely through numerical data. This qualitative phase added depth and context to the study, enriching our understanding of the subject matter.

Procedure

The process of gathering data was divided into multiple stages. The following steps were taken in order to conduct the study:

Quantitative Phase

An adapted questionnaire employed the quantitative phase to assess the teachers' cultural intelligence. It was given to a group of private school teachers working in private school in Kapalong.

Additionally, the researcher requested permission to the school administration with a letter where the teacher is working where the study being performed. The results will be added together, calculate, and analyze to confirm the findings of the qualitative data. The study's qualitative and quantitative phases carried out concurrently.

Qualitative Phase

In order to learn more about the lived experiences of these private school teachers about the inclusion of cultural intelligence into their learning, a one-on-one interview with the identified participants undertaken during the qualitative phase. Therefore, to assure the validity of the selection process, the researcher contacts the informants personally and inform them of the tasks to be complete, including the time allocated for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013).

Additionally, one-on-one or in-depth interviews with private school teachers individually answered the given question in order to provide a worthwhile chance for examining their perceptions of their experiences with cultural intelligence in learning. The researcher conducted these interviews with ten (10) teacher that were specifically chosen. Face-to-face in-depth interviews conducted, and the subjects' responses noted through audio-recording and taking extra notes of the answers.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

Mean and other descriptive statistics were used in the quantitative data

analysis to evaluate the respondents' average responses. After the survey questionnaires were retrieved, the total data was handled appropriately. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to perform additional descriptive and inferential statistical analysis on the survey data. This statistical procedure was used to determine the status of private school teachers' cultural intelligence.

Qualitative Data Analysis

The researcher used coding and thematic analysis for the qualitative data analysis. This involves looking at the patterns and themes that appear in the participants'/informants' comments or utterances during the focus groups and one-on-one interviews. The themes developed with the intention of analyzing the real-world cultural intelligence experiences of the private school teachers. The research aims that the participants' experiences in this setting were clarify through rigorous analysis of the data to identify and extract pertinent themes.

Ethical Considerations

In order to keep the trust of the private school teachers, the study's top priorities are safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality. I take steps to ensure that these ethical issues are thoughtfully addressed in order to maintain the participants' trust throughout the study.

The researcher is meticulously abiding by ethical principles including respect for others, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality in order to ensure that ethical requirements are met. The participants' rights and well-being are given high importance by these guidelines, which directing the study's conduct in a responsible and polite manner (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is a code of conduct that emphasizes the need of treating research participants with respect and decency and respecting their freedom to independently select whether or not to participate in a study. Participants must be fully aware of the study's goals, methods, risks, and advantages in order to follow this advice. Obtaining informed consent which is defined as willingly engaging into an agreement based on informed understanding it is necessary to uphold this principle. The researcher can make sure that the study is carried out morally and in a way that respects the rights and autonomy of the participants by respecting the concept of the respect for individuals (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

The researcher first obtains the participants' consent before starting the interviews in order to avoid schedule issues with their classes or other obligations. This is done to ensure that the researcher's presence does not interfere with the participants' schedules and to avoid

having to reschedule or cancelling the interviews.

As I conducted my research, I established a respectful and courteous rapport with the participants and requested their consent before recording any interactions. I also allow the participants to ask me questions whenever they want while maintaining the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews. Participants may also refuse not to respond to challenging questions. By getting to know the participants and treating them well, I've been able to conduct the study in an honest and polite manner.

Consent is fundamental to research ethics and show respect for study subjects. By obtaining their informed consent, participants were fully informed of the aims and purposes of the research they are being asked to participate in. In-depth interviews were conducted with the participants' consent, which was obtained in writing. They are informed of the study's findings and recommendations in order to maintain transparency and keep them inform (Creswell, 2012).

The researcher gave the participants letters of authorization and consent outlining the specifics of the study, including the techniques, design, and procedures, in order to assure the ethical conduct of the study. These letters are meant to clarify the study's parameters for participants so they can decide for themselves whether to join or not. Participants who choose not to participate may do so without giving a reason, and their information is keep private. The participant's right to know the study's findings is also disclosed by the researcher to them. The researcher can make sure that the study carries out in a responsible and respectful manner by adhering to these ethical principles.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, a lot of efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

In order to protect the beneficent principle, I take steps to maintain the anonymity and secrecy of the participants' remarks and personal information. To minimize any potential risks, I communicated well with the participants via social media rather than in-person meetings. By taking these actions, I've been able to protect the participants' interests and demonstrate my commitment to ethical research practices.

Additionally, the data collected for this research project is only used to achieve the study's objectives. However, alternative methods of communication or dissemination of the study's findings may also be used, such as presentation to the institution, publication in scholarly forums or journals, or presentation at conferences on a local, national, or international level. By disseminating the study's findings, the researcher wants to add to the body of knowledge in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, various approaches is used to arrive at results and conclusions, including the protection of individuals indicating that no identifiable information about the participants will be share. All materials, including audio recordings, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and other items, should be thrown away after the data has been analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect participant identities and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I used discrete coding to identify each participant's responses. This method calls for carefully framing any information that could be used to identify individuals by name, gender, race, or employment/location. By using suitable code and other protections. The researcher able to conceal the participants' identities and ensured that their privacy is being preserve.

Justice in conducting of this study it ensured that the participants' right to describe themselves as teachers working in private schools in Kapalong are upheld. Since the study's objective is to look at how cultural intelligence of teachers in teaching in the private school, with no minor teachers' rights violated. The researcher used a purposeful and random sampling techniques to ensure fairness participation opportunities. Teachers that teaching in private schools are given the option to decline; they are not force to participate. The volunteers have free snacks in exchange for their assistance and credit for participating to increase the study's effectiveness. Justice was also guaranteed by accurately transcribing and including participant statements that pertinent to the study goals (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phase. The first phase deals with the quantitative part in which it displays the status of private school teacher with regards on their cultural intelligence. The second phase deals with the qualitative part in which it was being presented thru a matrix form. The matrix shows the responses of the participants on their lived experiences regarding their cultural intelligence in teaching. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes and the supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Cultural Intelligence

Shown in Table 2 is the status of the cultural intelligence of private school teachers. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.23 with a

description of high. This means that the private school teachers manifested oftentimes their cultural intelligence. The variable of the study which is the cultural intelligence which has four indicators namely: strategy, knowledge, motivation and behavior.

Table 2. *Statuses of Cultural Intelligence*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Strategy		
1. Knowing what cultural knowledge, I utilize when engaging with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.	4.51	Very High
2. Adjusting my cultural knowledge when interacting with people from unfamiliar cultures.	4.37	Very High
3. Knowing the cultural knowledge I employ in cross-cultural interactions.	4.25	High
4. Verifying the accuracy of my cultural knowledge when engaging with individuals from different cultures.	4.36	Very High
5. Seeking feedback from individuals of different cultural backgrounds to ensure that my interactions are respectful and considerate of their cultural norms.	4.40	Very High
Category Mean	4.38	Very High
B. Knowledge		
1. Being knowledgeable of the rules (e.g., vocabulary, grammar) of other languages.	4.08	High
2. Being knowledgeable about the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures.	4.11	High
3. Being familiar with the arts and crafts of other cultures.	4.04	High
4. Being aware of the historical and social contexts that shape the cultural aspects of other societies.	4.14	High
5. Seeking actively to understand the perspectives of individuals from other cultures rather than making assumptions based on my own cultural background.	4.33	Very High
Category Mean	4.14	High
C. Motivation		
1. Being confident in my ability to socialize with locals in an unfamiliar culture.	4.14	High
2. Being confident that I can effectively manage the stresses associated with adjusting to a new culture.	4.10	High
3. Being able to find fulfillment in experiencing life within unfamiliar cultures	4.20	High
4. Being open-minded and receptive to learning about new cultures and ways of life.	4.40	Very High
5. Being adaptable and flexible when faced with unfamiliar cultural norms and practices	4.22	High
Category Mean	4.21	High
D. Behavior		
1. Changing my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires and needed it.	4.12	High
2. Using the pause and silence differently to suit in different cross-cultural situations.	4.15	High
3. Changing the way of my speaking when a cross-cultural situation requires it.	4.14	High
4. Changing my non-verbal behavior when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.	4.20	High
5. Changing my facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.	4.33	Very High
Category Mean	4.19	High
Overall Mean	4.23	High

Strategy. In terms of strategy, the category mean is 4.38, which is describe as very high. This means that it is always observed by the private school teacher. Among the items under this indicator, Item No. 1- Knowing for what cultural knowledge I utilize when engaging with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds got the highest mean of 4.51 which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the private school teachers. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the Item No. 3- Knowing the cultural knowledge I employ in cross-cultural interactions with a mean of 4.25. This rating is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers.

Knowledge. The knowledge was rated by the teachers as high, with a category mean of 4.14. This mean that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers. Among the items under this indicator, Item No. 5- Seeking actively to understand the perspectives of individuals from other cultures rather than making assumptions based on my own cultural background got the highest mean of 4.33, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the private school teachers. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the respondents was the Item No. 3- Being familiar with the arts and crafts of other cultures with a mean of 4.04. This rating is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers.

Motivation. The Motivation was rated by the respondents as high, with a category mean of 4.21. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers. Item No. 4- Being open-minded and receptive to learning about new cultures and ways of life garnered the highest rating with the mean 4.40, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the private school teachers. Conversely, Item No. 2- Being confident that I can effectively manage the stresses associated with adjusting to a new culture got the lowest mean of 4.10, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers.

Behavior. The behavior got the category mean 4.19, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers. The Item No. 5- Changing my facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it got the highest

mean of 4.33, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the private school teachers. Meanwhile, the Item No.1- Changing my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires and needed it is the lowest rated item which has a high category mean of 4.12. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the private school teachers.

The Lived Experiences of Private School Teacher with Regards to their Cultural Intelligence

There are four essential themes which are created based from the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question. The Table 3 deals on the private school teacher's personal experiences with the development of their cultural intelligence. A summary of the main themes that arose from the transcriptions of the participants' answers to the first study question is provided in the table mentioned above.

Table 3. Experiences of Private School Teachers with Regards to their Cultural Intelligence

Issues Probed	Core Ideas	Code/ Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Framework
The Need To Understand And Respect Diverse Cultural Background	Helping To Have A Smooth And Peaceful Class. Adapting To Individual's Culture To Understand Their Differences And Have A Culture-Sensitive Classroom. Being Aware Of The Cultural Background Of Each Student.	Adoption Of Culture Responsive Pedagogy	Embracing Culture Sensitive Classroom	Culturally Responsive Teaching Theory
	Respecting students' own denomination and cultural background in the teaching and learning process. Promoting diversity and inclusivity by understanding the distinct culture of the students. Familiarizing students' attitude to better establish connection and rapport with them.	Respecting Students' Distinct Culture		
Challenges in language barriers and expressing ideas in culturally diverse classroom	Preventing from expressing culturally diverse ideas in the class including language barriers and differing communication styles due to cultural differences. Limitations in sharing ideas due to varying culture of the students. Hindrances related to varying cultural norms and beliefs and even language barriers among students and the teacher. Having language barriers is a problem within the classroom and I adjusted my ways of teachings by using different methods Language barriers hindering effective communication and understanding of cultural backgrounds.	Conundrum in Expressing Thoughts and Ideas	Overcoming Cultural Hindrances and Language Barriers	Intercultural Competence Theory
	Preventing me from expressing my ideas inside in the class is the dialects that they are using because I can't communicate or converse them straightly.	Emerging Language Barriers		
Challenges in navigating cultural differences among students and strategies of the teacher to manage conflict arising from cultural differences of the students.	Misunderstanding in communication style and dilemma on how to properly address students. Being cautious about what is being discussed and talked inside the classroom as students are culturally sensitive. Employing active learning and cultural sensitivity counseling to facilitate understanding and resolution among students. Weighing things and avoiding being one-sided and find ourselves being neutral. Promoting open and respectful communication and encourage students to share their thoughts and experiences and mediate any conflicts that may arise.	Dilemma on Classroom Communication	Challenges and Techniques in Cultural Differences	Cultural Dimensions Theory
		Establishing a Welcoming Learning Environment		
Addressing Bias and Stereotypes in Teaching Culture Sensitive Classroom.	Being active in seeking and incorporating perspective of the students in the preparation of teaching materials. Teaching the students to respect one another by emphasizing the importance of respect in	Cultural Inclusivity and Respect	Strategies to Address Potential Biases and Stereotypes	Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity

preventing conflicts.

Letting students to feel included and belong in the class by emphasizing inclusivity among them regardless of their cultural background.

Looking at the performance of students objectively and treat them fairly regardless of their cultural background. Practicing Fair Treatment

Being open-minded and accepting ideas from all students who show interest in participating in class.

Avoiding discrimination by accepting and not ridiculing cultural differences.

Balancing cultural understanding and avoiding judgment from one another.

Embracing Culture Sensitive Classroom. In the context of cultural intelligence, some experiences experienced by the teacher are adopting culturally responsive pedagogy and understanding and respect for diversity of students. It was mentioned by the participants that with the help of cultural intelligence they can create a setting that is culturally sensitive that embrace students' diversity.

Adoption of Culture Responsive Pedagogy. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Teacher expressed common responses on cultural intelligence in academic context. Most of them stated that cultural intelligence made them adopted the different culture of students to create a culturally responsive pedagogy.

Similarly, Participant 1 recognized the helpfulness of being culturally intelligent when it comes in teaching. Through culturally intelligence the teacher have a smooth and peaceful class. This highlights the importance of being culturally intelligent in peaceful learning for students. As participant 1 stated that:

“Cultural intelligence is maka tabang jud na siya sa imoha... para kanang hapsay, at peace ang imohang kanang klase.” (IDI-01)

(Cultural intelligence help me to have a smooth and peaceful class.)

Moreover, the utilization of cultural intelligence shows great significance to educators in having greater understanding about their student. By being able to adapt and understand the diverse culture of their student, teacher can assist themselves to understand their students' differences. It is clear that being cultural intelligent is a great enhancement for their teaching. As what Participant 4 said that:

“I think cultural intelligence helps me in my teaching profession by maybe adapting their culture, for us nga makabalo ta og unsa jod ka lahi-lahi-an and didto nato ma show karun kung asa ta pwede mo lugar.” (IDI-04)

(I think cultural intelligence helps me in my teaching profession by maybe adapting to each individual's culture to understand their differences, and through this we can show where we can meet.)

In addition, cultural intelligence has played a crucial role in enabling teacher to understand their student's cultural background. By being culturally intelligent teacher are being aware and understand the students' differences. Integrating cultural intelligence in teaching ensures continuous understanding and awareness in various circumstances. Participant 7 stated that:

“As teacher it can help us to be more aware of what is their culture and to respect their differences.” (IDI-07)

(As a teacher it can help us to be more aware of their culture and respect their differences.)

Respecting Students' Distinct Culture. This is the second code of the first probed issue. IDI participants imparted that using cultural intelligence can help them enhance their understanding and respect for the student's diversity. Private school teacher uses cultural intelligence because it helps them to be more efficient in classroom setting by respecting the different cultural background of the students.

Furthermore, the utilization of cultural intelligence also allows the teacher to have respect in whatever denomination and cultural background that their student have. Cultural intelligence can act as support for teacher to adjust in the different denomination of the students. As what Participant 1 said that:

“So, whatever denomination and cultural background, we need to adjust and we need to respect them specially sa mga denomination.” (IDI-01)

(So, whatever denomination and cultural background, we need to adjust and respect them specially in their denomination.)

Correspondingly, being cultural intelligence help the teacher to understand and respect the diversity of the learners. As a result, it will be easy for them enhances the teachers' teaching methods and also by influencing the students by promoting inclusivity in the classroom settings. Just like Participant 10 said:

“Being cultural intelligence help me in my teaching profession because it helps me understand and respect diversity it also enhances my teaching methods and influence students by promoting inclusivity, effective communication and it helps me understand to respect

and cater cultural diversity of our students.” (IDI-10)

(Being culturally intelligent help my teaching profession to understand and respect diversity, it also enhances my teaching methods and influencing students by promoting inclusivity, effective communication and it help me understand, respect and cater the diversity of students.)

Lastly, Participant 5 highlights the importance of familiarizing the students’ attitude as it will help them know and aware of their student’s behavior. By being culturally intelligent helps the teacher know when and where to engage with these diverse students, allowing them to familiarize their student to have a meaningful teaching and learning interaction. She stated that:

“Cultural intelligence helps me in my teaching profession by familiarizing my student’s attitude, nakakatulong ito para know more about my student’s para kilalanin mabuti yung mga studyante ko.” (IDI-05)

(Cultural intelligence helps me in my teaching profession by familiarizing students’ attitude and help to know more about students and understand them better.)

Overcoming Cultural Hindrances and Language Barriers. In the context of cultural intelligence, it is important to overcome different hindrances and language barriers in a classroom setting. By recognizing and respecting students’ cultural differences, we can create an environment where students feel comfortable in expressing themselves. This helps to bridge communication gaps and encourages active participation, leading to a more inclusive and effective learning experience for all students.

Conundrum in Expressing Thoughts and Ideas. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants mentioned that there are some hindrances that hinder them from expressing their ideas in a classroom setting. This hindrance includes the language barriers, beliefs and students’ communication styles. These hindrances can impede teachers’ ability to have an effective and engaging classroom discussions and activities.

In relation to that, the participant 7 mentioned that the hindrances that prevent teacher in expressing ideas includes language differences and differing communication styles that can cause potential misunderstandings within the students. As she stated that:

“Hindrances that prevent me from expressing my ideas inside the class that is culturally diverse may include language barriers, differing communication styles, and potential misunderstandings due to cultural differences.” (IDI-07)

Additionally, things that hinder educators in expressing their ideas inside the classroom are the students’ beliefs and tradition. It is really difficult for the teacher to address the differences of the students specifically that they are diverse in terms of their cultural background, beliefs and tradition. As participant 8 said:

“The hindrances that prevent me of course their beliefs and tradition, if ever this belief is acceptable in me and other students but not for them.” (IDI-08)

Lastly, in a culturally diverse classroom, teachers may encounter hindrances such as the fear of unintentionally offending students, misinterpreting cultural norms, and language barriers. Teacher encounters such difficulties and hindrances it’s because of the students’ differences in a class that prevent them in expressing their ideas. As participant 3 said:

“There are different and many hindrances but some of those are fear of unintentional offending learners, misinterpreting cultural norms and of course the language barriers.” (IDI-03)

Emerging Language Barriers. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants from IDI mentioned that open communication in a culturally diverse classroom involves creating an environment where students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and ideas. Language barriers can hinder open communication as students have different dialects.

Similarly, teacher struggle in the various dialects that the students have, as they are from different cultural background. Having language barriers is really a problem that they faced within the classroom and by that teacher adjusting their ways of teachings by using different methods. As participant 1 said:

“...student nato nga gikan pa from indigenous people. So, naay uban dli kaau jud as in ka makasabot og English, di kasabot og Bisaya kaau, ikaw dapat mag adjust jud ka pag teacher ka. Mangita jud kog mga differentiated activity nga maha-om sa ilahang learning style.” (IDI-01)

(...We have student that is indigenous people, there are some can’t understand English and some cannot understand Bisaya. So, I adjusted my ways of teachings by using different methods that fit in their learning style.)

Moreover, in order to effectively engage the culturally diverse students in lessons, teacher is adjusting their teaching strategies to ensure that students feel a sense of belonging by creating a supportive and respectful classroom environment where students feel valued and understood. As participant 4 said:

“I think is their language kay dili man pod ta tanan nga ingana jodka kabalo og kahawud sa ilahang mga culture specially jod kanang mga language sometimes dili kaau nato mapa gawas kung unsay gusto natong e-abot sa ilaha. Ato-a silang hibalo-on or suta-on jod nato

ang ilahang gigikanan, I mean kanang ilahang mga culture.” (IDI-04)

(I think is their language because not all are good at English sometimes their language hinders effective communication and understanding of cultural their backgrounds.)

Lastly, having students who have different dialect is one of the things that hinder the teacher in having an effective communication in classroom settings. The students’ dialects made it difficult for the teacher to communicate or to have a conversation with the students straightly. As participant 5 said:

“The hindrance that prevents me from expressing my ideas inside in the class is that, the dialects that they using because I can't communicate them straightly.” (IDI-05)

(The hindrances that prevent me from expressing my ideas inside the class is the dialects that they are using because, I cannot communicate them well.)

Challenges and Techniques in Cultural Differences. In the context of cultural intelligence, teacher face challenges in understanding and respecting diverse cultural backgrounds of their students. To cope with cultural differences, teachers can seek professional development and opportunities in creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that welcome cultural diversity.

Dilemma on Classroom Communication. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants mentioned that there are many challenges that they face in teaching student who are culturally diverse and have different backgrounds and how they can address those diversity or differences.

In relation to that, teacher address misunderstandings, communication styles and conflicts by adapting to my students' cultural backgrounds. This involves learning about different cultural norms and communication styles, and being open to resolving conflicts in a culturally sensitive manner. By doing so, teacher can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. As participant 3 said:

“Misunderstanding, communication style and conflict and how do I address them. I adapt the culture of my students and so they are and we meet halfway so that we will have a meaningful teaching-learning process.” (IDI-03)

(I address the misunderstanding, communication style and conflict by adapting the culture of my students for us to meet halfway to have a meaningful teaching-learning process)

Additionally, it's important to be mindful of cultural sensitivities and to avoid unintentionally causing hurt or offense with our words or jokes. Students from different cultural backgrounds may have varying levels of sensitivity to certain topics, so it's crucial to approach interactions with awareness and sensitivity to create a more inclusive and respectful learning environment. As Participant 5 said:

“So, that is why we have to be cautious lalo na sa atong mga gina pang istorya kay wata kabalo basig sakit na para sa ila tas akoa joke lang nya sa ilaha. Sensitive kaau sila.” (IDI-05)

(So, that is why we have to be cautious, especially in what we talk about because we never know if it might hurt them, and what may just be a joke for me could be painful for them. They are very sensitive.)

Lastly, having cultural differences teacher adapted teaching methods to accommodate language barriers in the classroom. This includes using various instructional strategies to ensure that all students, regardless of language proficiency, can effectively engage with the material and participate in the learning process. As Participant 9 said:

“So, the language barriers so kato siya nga problems within the classroom I adjusted my ways of teachings by using different methods.” (IDI-09)

(So, the language barrier is the problem within the classroom, I adjusted my ways of teaching by using different methods.)

Establishing a Welcoming Learning Environment. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants from IDI mentioned that, utilizing active listening, empathy, and open communication manage conflicts that arise in the classroom. Addressing issues promptly, encourage respectful dialogue, and work towards finding constructive solutions that prioritize the well-being and learning of all students is how teacher cope up with the situation.

Similarly, teacher employ active learning strategies to engage students in hands-on, participatory activities that promote understanding and empathy. Teacher incorporates cultural sensitivity counseling to address conflicts, promoting an environment where students can learn from each other's diverse perspectives and work towards peaceful resolution. As Participant 3 said:

“I employ active learning and cultural sensitivity counseling to facilitate understanding and resolution among the students.” (IDI-03)

(I will employ active learning and counseling for cultural sensitivity to facilitate understanding and resolution among students.)

Moreover, it is really important to avoid taking sides in conflicts instead strive to find a balanced approach. This means weighing

different perspectives and helping students see the merit in multiple viewpoints, encouraging open-mindedness and foster respectful dialogue for constructive resolution. As Participant 2 said:

“I must not be one-sided kumbaga we should weigh things and you should be in the between of them.” (IDI-02)

(I must not be one-sided, we should weigh things and avoiding being one-sided, we should find ourselves in between them.)

Lastly, it's crucial to create an environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves openly, while also providing guidance in resolving conflicts peacefully. Encouraging respectful communication and facilitating discussions helps students learn from each other's perspectives and fosters a positive and inclusive classroom community. As Participant 7 said:

“I use active listening, empathy, and patience to understand the perspectives of my students. I also promote open and respectful communication, encourage students to share their thoughts and experiences, and mediate any conflicts that may arise.” (IDI-07)

Strategies to Address Potential Biases and Stereotypes. In the context of cultural intelligence teacher have a positive comment on the strategies they employ to address potential biases and stereotypes in culturally diverse classroom. It is important to address potential biases and stereotypes in teaching by promoting critical thinking and empathy to have a more harmonious environment wherein students can learn effectively.

Cultural Inclusivity and Respect. This is the first code for fourth probed issue. Many of the participants share the same experiences of the usefulness cultural intelligence in making strategy to have cultural inclusivity and respect as a teacher involves recognizing and valuing the diversity of students' backgrounds, beliefs, and traditions. This can be achieved by acknowledging and learning about different cultural practices, and promoting open dialogue and understanding among students.

In addition, actively seeking out and incorporating diverse perspectives into teaching materials and discussions by ensuring that students are exposed to a wide range of viewpoints and experiences. This helps create a more inclusive and enriching learning environment, fostering empathy and critical thinking skills in the students. As Participant 3 said:

“I actively seek out and incorporate perspective into my teaching materials and I apply it in my discussion.” (IDI-03)

In connection with that, teaching students to respect one another is a foundational strategy for addressing potential biases in the classroom. By emphasizing the importance of respect, I create a positive and inclusive learning environment were students feel valued and understood, reducing the likelihood of conflicts based on biases or misunderstandings. As Participant 5 said:

“The very first strategy that i have employed to address potential biases is gina tun-an jud nako akong nga studyante to respect one another, we have to respect them para wala nay gubot na mahitabo.” (IDI-05)

(The very first strategy that I have employed to address potential biases is teaching my students to respect one another, emphasizing the importance of respect to prevent conflicts.)

Lastly, emphasizing inclusivity and ensuring all students feel included regardless of their cultural background is crucial for creating a positive and supportive learning environment. By doing so, it promotes a sense of belonging and validate each student's unique identity, which helps to counteract potential biases and fosters a culture of respect and appreciation for diversity in the classroom. As Participant 9 said:

“Let them feel that they are included or belong in your class and let them feel that they are not different from the other students it's because we are here to teach them whatever the cultural background they have.” (IDI-09)

Practicing Fair Treatment. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. Participants consider cultural intelligence as a way to interact and treat with student fairly. It is important to create a safe and supportive environment where each student feels valued and has equal access to learning opportunities.

In that sense, teacher approach students' performance objectively, without letting personal biases or preconceptions influence evaluations. By treating all students fairly, regardless of their cultural background, and remaining open-minded to ideas, teacher can create an inclusive and supportive learning environment where each student feels valued and respected. As Participant 8 said:

“...with regards to biases I should look on students' performance objectively not subjectively regardless of their culture or opinion I should be open-minded to everyone I should be fair in treating them regardless of who they are where they come from, what are their cultural bases and as long as they are showing interest in the school and they are participating then I will accept their ideas.” (IDI-09)

In addition, it is crucial for teacher to respect students' cultural backgrounds and actively avoid discrimination. By accepting and not ridiculing cultural differences, I create an inclusive and welcoming environment where students feel valued and respected. As Participant 10 said:

“Kinahanglan kung unsa ilahang culture kay diha man jod na mag kuan sa atong mga tribu. So, we need to respect dawaton nato and dli kataw-an.” (IDI-10)

(Should respecting students' cultural backgrounds and avoiding discrimination. Accept and not ridicule cultural differences.)

Lastly, balancing cultural understanding and avoid passing judgment is important. This means being open-minded, respecting diverse perspectives, and creating a safe space for students to express their cultural identities without fear of criticism. It can promote inclusivity and mutual respect in the classroom, fostering an environment where all students feel valued and understood. As Participant 4 said:

“Balancing cultural understanding and avoiding judgment. Incorporating cultural activities or symposiums to facilitate mutual understanding and respect among students.” (IDI-04)

The Insights that Teachers Share in Developing Cultural intelligence

Displayed in Table 4 are the responses of the participants with regards to their insight of the challenges faced in developing cultural intelligence during their professional academic work. There are four essential themes which are drawn out from the in-depth of the participants for the second question. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table.

Table 4. Insights that Teachers Share regarding in Developing Cultural Intelligence

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Exploring the Role of Cultural Intelligence in Private School Education.	Being crucial for teachers in private schools to handle students’ diverse culture and avoiding conflicts with parents. Understanding cultural diversity particularly among Indigenous Peoples (IP) and widen teachers' perspectives, emotional intelligence, and patience. Recognizing and developing cultural intelligence as it is vital for teachers to understand and connect with students' cultures and backgrounds to facilitate learning effectively.	Importance of Cultural Intelligence in Teaching	Fostering Culture Responsive Teaching	Culturally Responsive Teaching
Recommendations for improving cultural intelligence in the classroom.	Being essential in creating an inclusive learning environment, adopting teaching methods, and fostering mutual respect among students from diverse cultural backgrounds. Leading to collaborative and harmonious classrooms where teachers can incorporate diverse learning styles to meet students' needs. Giving the opportunity to experience seminars, like behavioral seminars. Being empathetic and sympathetic with the students, especially those who are member of the IP community. Improving their cultural intelligence in the classroom to actively seek opportunities for cultural learning and self-reflection. Teacher should be open to new learnings by attending trainings and seminars involving cultural intelligence. Undergoing certain seminars to gain more knowledge, insights, and strategies for teaching. Learning about different cultures, traditions, and perspectives, as well as examining biases and assumptions.	Practical Implementation in the Classroom Empowering Professional Development Developing Cultural Intelligence	Enhancing Teacher Competence in Cultural Understanding	Cultural Intelligence Theory
Impact of Incorporating Culturally Diverse Perspectives on Student Learning and Perspective	Having patience and widening one’s knowledge about students' backgrounds to avoid conflict of interest. Creating a classroom environment where cultural sensitivity is prioritized leading to a meaningful interaction in the classroom. Having a deeper understanding of students' cultural backgrounds. Incorporating culturally diverse perspectives to break down boundaries among students. Understanding students' cultural backgrounds	Fostering an Inclusive and Culture Sensitive Classroom Impact on Student Learning and Perspective	Fostering Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusive Education	Intercultural competence model

Impact of Culturally Responsive Teaching Strategies and building relationship	<p>and incorporating diverse perspectives to have a significant student learning outcome. Meeting the learning needs of students by integrating strategies that make them feel included and engaged.</p> <p>Including culture diversity in the classroom and have the opportunity to know one's students. Knowing each student from where they came from, what languages they speak, studying their beliefs, culture, and traditions.</p> <p>Learning to love your students as your own, though we have culturally diverse students. Embracing the diverse nature of the students by embracing their culture, beliefs, and traditions. Being fair, without bias in treating all the students. Also, be empathetic and sympathetic with them.</p>	Advises for Teaching Culturally Diverse Students	Inclusion of Culture in the Curriculum	Multicultural Education Theory
		Building Relationships and Understanding Cultural Backgrounds		

Fostering Culture Responsive Teaching. Based on the similar responses from the participants, the private school teacher's insight according to their cultural intelligence is provided. According to the participants' information, culturally responsive teaching entails acknowledging, honoring, and incorporating students varied cultural origins into the educational process.

Importance of Cultural Intelligence in Teaching. For the first investigated issue, this is the first code. Teachers that possess cultural intelligence are better able to relate to and comprehend students from a variety of cultural backgrounds. Teachers can establish inclusive learning environments, modify their pedagogical approaches to accommodate the requirements of every student, and cultivate a sense of respect and belonging in the classroom by cultivating cultural intelligence.

Similarly, cultural intelligence is crucial for teachers in private schools as it enables them to understand and connect with students from diverse backgrounds. This helps in creating an inclusive and respectful learning environment, reducing misunderstandings, and building positive relationships with students and their families. As Participant 1 said:

"Cultural intelligence is every important specially in private school teacher it's because, once gani nga dli nato ma handle sila, ilahang parents then mag warak na dayun na diri." (IDI-01)

(Cultural intelligence is every important specially in private school teacher it is because, once you can't handle diverse student populations effectively and it can cause conflicts with parents.)

Moreover, understanding cultural diversity among Indigenous Peoples can help you develop a deeper perspective and empathy for your students. It can also help you to be more patient and understanding when working with students from diverse cultural backgrounds. As Participant 2 said:

"...we considered this IPs who are really included in this culturally diverse it is very important because it widen me particularly with understanding with our IPs students." (IDI-02)

Additionally, having cultural intelligence is essential for understanding and connecting with students from diverse backgrounds. It enables you to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, leading to more effective communication and teaching strategies that resonate with all students. As Participant 4 said:

"...maka balo ta sa cultural intelligences or culturally diverse nila og mas importante jod na maka balo para ma develop nato ang atang kahibalo when it comes sa ilahang mga culture pinaagi ana hibaw-on jod nato or suta-on jod nato ilang matag usa nga culture." (IDI-04)

(Recognizing and developing cultural intelligence is vital for teachers to understand and connect with students' cultures and backgrounds to facilitate learning effectively.)

Practical Implementation in the Classroom. This is the second code for the first probed issue. It involves actively seeking to understand and learn about the cultural backgrounds of their students, incorporating diverse perspectives into their teaching materials and methods, and being open and flexible in addressing cultural differences. Ongoing professional development and training related to cultural competency can help teachers continually improve their cultural intelligence.

With regards to that, being culturally intelligent enables teachers to better understand their students' cultural backgrounds and address their needs and concerns. This understanding also helps teachers communicate effectively with students from diverse cultural backgrounds, ultimately promoting a positive and enriching learning experience for all students. As participant 5 said:

"It helps us to understand different cultures so, makatabang sa amoa para masabtan namo among mga studyante, kung unsa man ilahang mga hinaing, pwede sila maka istorya sa amoa." (IDI-05)

(It helps teachers understand students' cultures and address their concerns they can talk to us.)

Aside from that, in a private school setting, cultural intelligence is crucial for teachers to create an inclusive learning environment by understanding and respecting the diverse cultural backgrounds of their students. It helps teachers adapt their teaching methods to meet the needs of students from different cultures and fosters mutual respect among students, contributing to a positive and harmonious classroom setting. As participant 7 said:

“The importance of cultural intelligence for a teacher in a private school cannot be overstated. Private schools often have a diverse student body, and cultural intelligence is essential for creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment. It enables teachers to understand and connect with students from different cultural backgrounds, adapt their teaching methods, and foster mutual respect and understanding among students.” (IDI-07)

Lastly, culturally intelligent teaching allows for the creation of collaborative and harmonious classrooms by recognizing and embracing diverse learning styles. The enables teachers to effectively tailor their teaching methods to meet the individual needs of students, promoting a supportive and inclusive learning environment for everyone. As participant 8 said:

“Cultural intelligence is indeed very important, once you are culturally intelligent this will able us teachers to become more or it will lead us to a collaborative and harmonious classroom environment. So, by this you are aware that you have diverse learners so that’s the time you are going to incorporate different learning styles also that will cater their different learning styles and need.” (IDI-08)

Enhancing Teacher Competence in Cultural Understanding. In the context of developing cultural intelligence during their professional academic work. Participants have shared their insight on how to enhance cultural intelligence.

Empowering Professional Development. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Participants stated that in order to have professional development, teachers need to participate in workshops or training sessions focused on cultural competency in the classroom. Attend seminars and training to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment for all students.

In connection with that, Participant 2 recommend for educators teaching with students who are have Indigenous People (IPs), it is important to practice patience, empathy, and understanding. Taking the time to understand each student, and putting oneself in their shoes, can help to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. She said that:

“I guess, recommendation for other educators specially who’s students are like us who have IPs students, I guess be patience and if possible, understand their situation and put yourself in their shoes and also you need to intindihin mo kung ano sila.” (IDI-02)

(I guess, recommendation for other educators specially who’s students are like us who have IPs students, I guess be patience and if possible, understand their situation and put yourself in their shoes and also you need to understand who they are.)

Furthermore, to improve cultural intelligence in the classroom, educators should actively seek opportunities for cultural learning and self-reflection. This involves exploring diverse perspectives, engaging in conversations with colleagues and students from different backgrounds, and reflecting on personal biases and assumptions. By continuously learning and self-reflecting, teachers can create a more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment. As participant 7 said:

“My recommendation for other educators to improve their cultural intelligence in the classroom is to actively seek out opportunities for cultural learning and self-reflection.” (IDI-07)

Developing Cultural Intelligence. This is the second code for the probed issue. Participants stated that in order to gain and develop cultural intelligence it involves actively seeking opportunities for cultural learning and engaging in conversations with individuals from diverse backgrounds. Continuous self-reflection and a willingness to learn and grow are key to developing cultural intelligence in the classroom.

In relation to that, Participant 3 said being open to new learnings and attending trainings and seminars on cultural intelligence is essential for creating a more inclusive and culturally responsive classroom. This helps educators understand and respect the diverse backgrounds of their students, leading to better communication, empathy, and support for all learners. She said that:

“Teacher should be open for new learnings, attend trainings and seminars that involve cultural intelligence.” (IDI-03)

Additionally, attending seminars can provide teachers with valuable knowledge, insights, and strategies to enhance their cultural intelligence. By participating in these seminars, educators can gain a deeper understanding of how to effectively engage with students from diverse backgrounds, adapt teaching methods, and create a more inclusive learning environment. As participant 8 said:

“...to gain more knowledge about a specific culture of course we need to undergo certain seminars and by that seminar we can gain more knowledge and also insight and strategies from that seminar na among na gain amo-a siyang ma incorporate sa among mga klases.” (IDI-08)

(...To gain more knowledge about a specific culture of course we need to undergo certain seminars and by that seminar we can gain more knowledge and also insight and strategies from that seminar that we can gain and incorporate in your classes.)

Lastly, as a teacher, it's important to actively learn about different cultures, traditions, and perspectives. This helps in examining biases and assumptions, allowing educators to create a more inclusive and respectful learning environment for all students. As participant 7 said:

“This can involve learning about different cultures, traditions, and perspectives, as well as examining biases and assumptions. Building relationships with students from diverse backgrounds and being open to feedback and dialogue is also crucial.” (IDI-07)

Fostering Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusive Education. The insight of private school teacher in terms of creating a culturally sensitive and inclusive education. Cultural sensitivity in education involves recognizing and respecting the diverse backgrounds, traditions, and perspectives of students. Inclusive education aims to create learning environments that embrace and support all students, regardless of their cultural backgrounds.

Fostering an Inclusive and Culture Sensitive Classroom. This is the first code of the third probed issue. Culturally sensitive and inclusive teaching means adapting your methods to meet the needs of all students, regardless of their cultural, linguistic, or learning differences, and actively working to create a supportive and equitable learning environment for everyone.

In connection to this, Participant 1 said that it's important to have patience and be open to learning about your students' backgrounds. This helps to avoid being blindsided by assumptions and allows you to better understand and support your students. She said that:

“...maka gain jod ta og pasensya gamay, ma widen atong knowledge, labi na kung kanang kahibalo ta kung unsa ang mga bata nga naa sa ato-a kay dili ta pwede nga magpaka blind perme.” (IDI-01)

(...We can gain to have patience and widen our knowledge, especially about the students' backgrounds, to avoid being blindsided.)

In addition, prioritizing cultural sensitivity in the classroom fosters meaningful interactions and learning experiences for students from diverse backgrounds. By recognizing and valuing students' cultural differences, teachers can create an inclusive environment that promotes understanding and respect for all students. As Participant 8 said:

“As teachers if we are just being culturally sensitive then we could create a classroom environment where everything is open and a meaningful classroom environment since dealing with different cultural perspective individual you cannot only impart but you can also learn from those different cultures of your students.” (IDI-08)

(As a teacher, being culturally sensitive we can create a classroom environment that is open since dealing with different cultural perspective of individual you're not only imparting but you are also learning from those diverse culture of the students.)

Lastly, having a deeper understanding of students' cultural backgrounds helps us broaden our perspectives and avoid making judgmental assumptions. This balance allows us to create a supportive environment where all students feel respected and valued, leading to more effective teaching and learning experiences. As participant 4 said:

“...mas nindot jod nga mas daghan tag mahibal-an when it comes sa ilahang culture kay para mas mapa lawak pa gud nato ang ato-ang mga huna-huna, mas mahibalo pa jod ta kung unsa jod ang ilahang gigikanan nga mga culture para lagi pag abot pod sa time dili ta ingon-ana ka pataka nalang og judge nga mali ni. Dapat ano jod ta ma'am is kanang balance jod gihapon ta.” (IDI-04)

(...it is better to have a lot of knowledge when it comes in students' cultural backgrounds to broaden our perspectives to know where they came from so that when the time comes, we can avoid judgment. We need to strike a balance.)

Impact on Student Learning and Perspective. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Understanding students' cultural backgrounds can have a significant impact on their learning and perspective. It can help teachers tailor their instruction to be more relevant and inclusive, leading to increased engagement and academic success. It encourages students to appreciate diversity and mutual respect among peers.

In connection, incorporating culturally diverse perspectives in the classroom helps break down boundaries among students by creating an inclusive environment where everyone's background is understood and valued. Embracing cultural diversity help create a welcoming space where students feel seen, heard, and valued, ultimately enhancing their learning experience. As participant 2 said:

“Incorporating culturally diverse perspectives has helped break down boundaries among students and fostered inclusivity leading to a more understanding and accepting environment.” (IDI-02)

(Incorporating culturally diverse perspectives helped breakdown boundaries among the students and to fostered inclusivity leading to a more understanding and accepting environment.)

Further, understanding students' cultural backgrounds and incorporating diverse perspectives in teaching can impact strategies by making them more relevant and engaging for students. Enhancing the effectiveness of instruction and contribute to positive academic results. As participant 6 said:

“Incorporating culturally diverse perspective in my teaching pag impart nako sa akong knowledge for them because the integration or the transmission of the knowledge of the teacher to students is not easy. It brings different techniques and strategies para mabuhay or

mahitabo na siya.” (IDI-06)

(Incorporating culturally diverse perspective in my teaching in imparting my knowledge to them because the integration or transmission of the knowledge of the teacher to students is not easy. It brings different techniques and strategies to doo or to make it happen.)

Lastly, meeting the learning needs of students involves integrating strategies that make them feel included and engaged. This approach fosters a sense of belonging and motivation, ultimately leading to better understanding and improved learning outcomes. As participant 9 said:

“If you will deliver your lessons in an effective way wherein, they can feel that they belong to that certain class or topic and kanang ma feel jod nimo nga mas naka tuon ang bata kay ingani ang strategy nga gi integrate. Ma feel nila na they are belong sa imohang class.” (IDI-09)

(If you will deliver your lessons in an effective way wherein, they can feel that they belong to that certain class or topic and you can feel that your student is really learning if you use that specific strategy that you integrate. They can feel that they are belong to the class.)

Inclusion of Culture in the Curriculum. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview with the categories of advises for teaching culturally diverse students and building relationships and understanding cultural backgrounds. The participants mentioned the importance of embracing cultural diversity in education.

Advises for Teaching Culturally Diverse Students. This is the first code of the fourth probed issue. In-depth interview participants imparted advises for teaching culturally diverse students. They shared insight in incorporating culturally relevant teaching materials, patient, fostering a welcoming environment that celebrates diversity, adapting teaching strategies to accommodate different learning styles.

Moreover, Participant 7 said that embracing diversity in the classroom allows for a richer learning experience. It's crucial for teachers to recognize and appreciate the diverse backgrounds and perspectives of their students. By doing so, they can create an inclusive environment that fosters mutual respect and understanding. Embracing diversity also provides opportunities for teachers to learn from their students and to have growth. She stated that:

“Embrace the diversity present in the classroom and use it as an opportunity for learning and growth, both for yourself and your students. Seek support and resources to better understand and accommodate cultural differences, and be open to feedback from students and colleagues.” (IDI-07)

(Embracing the diversity present in the classroom and use it as an opportunity for learning and growth for the teacher and students. Seek support and resources to better understand and accommodate cultural differences, and being open for feedback from the students and colleagues.)

Further, knowing their students' backgrounds, teachers can better support their academic growth. Knowing their beliefs, culture, and traditions is essential. This understanding also helps in building meaningful connections with students. As participant 8 said:

“By knowing where they came from, what are there languages of course we can already know what are their beliefs, what are their culture, what are their tradition and once we already know that one, then that’s the time that we could incorporate a meaningful activity wherein they are welcome, they are not hesitant and they are not afraid to show or to share their beliefs towards their classmates.” (IDI-08)

(By knowing where they came from, what are there language we can already know what are their beliefs, culture, tradition and by that, we can incorporate a meaningful activity wherein students feel welcome and not hesitant to show and share their beliefs towards their classmates.)

Building Relationships and Understanding Cultural Backgrounds. This is the second code for the fifth probed issue. Participants share that building relationship and understanding allows to better connect with students, recognize their individual needs, and adapt their teaching to be more effective and relevant.

To add, embracing a mindset of care and compassion for each student as if they were your own can help create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment. Offering prayers for students, it demonstrates a genuine concern for their well-being and can foster connection and respect. As participant 2 said:

“I can could say is learn to love your students as your own, even though we have culturally diverse students learn to love them as your own, pray for them it is because that is the only thing you can help them and of course the devotion and the commitment in the teaching profession.” (IDI-02)

Moreover, embracing students' culture and showing respect helps to establish trust and understanding, which in turn can enhance their learning experience and overall well-being. It also demonstrates our commitment to upholding our responsibilities as educators. As participant 5 said:

“...dapat e-embrace nato kay students mn nato sila,naa may tay gipanompaan na mga tungkulin so dapat ato jud na syang panindigan so ana lang e-embrace ang mga bata ang ilahang kultura og respuon.” (IDI-05)

(...should embrace them because they are our students, and we have responsibilities assigned to us, so we should uphold them. Thus, we should embrace the children, their culture, and respect them.)

Lastly, it's crucial to be fair and unbiased when working with culturally diverse students. Recognizing that everyone is struggling to navigate cultural differences, it's important to empathize and put ourselves in their shoes. As participant 10 said:

“Mastorya lang jod nako is always be fair walay bias kay kita man gud tanan naga struggle jod ta sa pag deal sa mga culturally diverse students so kinahanglan e-put nato ang atong shoes sa ilahang shoes para masabtan nato ang ilahang mga gina sunod.” (IDI-10)

(I could only say that always being fair, without bias because we're all struggling to deal with culturally diverse students so we need to put ourselves in their shoes to understand their actions.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

This study utilizes a mixed methods technique with a convergent parallel methodology to examine the cultural intelligence of teachers in all private schools in Maniki, Kapalong. Corroboration of the results from the quantitative and qualitative phases is the third research question in the study. The focal points of the study are listed in the first column of Table 5 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings. The quantitative and qualitative findings are then listed in the second and third columns. While the qualitative findings, which indicate the identified answers, confirm or contradict the quantitative results, the quantitative phase’s findings are often the indicators with the highest mean. The nature of the data integration is shown in the fourth column, and the axiological conclusions drawn from the data presented in the previous columns are shown in the fifth column.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Using Cultural intelligence in Teaching	On Table 1.1 under the indicator knowledge with overall mean of 4.14, is rated as High, specifically in item number 2- being knowledgeable about the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures (M= 4.11; High)	On Table 3.1, under the essential theme Embracing Culture Sensitive Classroom specifically in first category, Adoption of Culture Responsive Pedagogy, core idea number 3- Being aware of the cultural background of each student.	Merging – converging	The result of both quantitative and qualitative shows that private school teachers really imply understanding and respecting diverse cultures in their teaching. They really want to make sure that all students feel included and valued in classroom setting. They also use different teaching methods such as, active learning and being sensitive to cultural differences of the students, this helps them create a welcoming atmosphere where everyone can communicate and interact effectively. Teachers also learn to adapt and handle any issues fairly by promoting respect and being open to learn more about different cultures. This highlight how important it is for a teacher to be culturally aware to make sure all students feel welcome, understood and included in school.
	On Table 1.1 under the indicator Strategy with overall mean of 4.38, is rated as Very High, specifically in item number 1- knowing what cultural knowledge I utilize when engaging with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds which got the highest mean of, which describe as Very High.	On Table 3.2, under the first category, Practical Implementation of Cultural Intelligence core idea number 1- Being essential in creating an inclusive learning environment, adopting teaching methods, and fostering mutual respect among students from diverse cultural backgrounds.	Merging – converging	
	On Table 1.1 under the indicator motivation with overall mean of 4.21, is rated as High, specifically in item number 5- being adaptable and flexible when faced with unfamiliar cultural norms and practices (M= 4.22; High)	On Table 3.1, under the essential theme Embracing Culture Sensitive Classroom specifically in first category, Adoption of Culture Responsive Pedagogy, core idea number 2- Adapting to individual’s culture to understand their differences and have a culture-sensitive classroom.	Merging – converging	
	On Table 1.1 under the indicator behavior with overall mean of 4.19, is rated as High, specifically in item number 5- changing my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires and needed it. (M= 4.33; Very High)	On Table 3.1, under the second category, Emerging Language Barriers core idea number 1- Having language barriers is a problem within the classroom and I adjusted my ways of teachings by using different methods.	Merging – converging	
	On Table 1.1 under the indicator strategy with overall mean of 4.38,			

is rated as Very High, specifically in item number 3- knowing the cultural knowledge I employ in cross-cultural interactions. (M= 4.25; High)	On Table 3.1, under the second category, Establishing a Welcoming Learning Environment core idea number 1- Employing active learning and cultural sensitivity counseling to facilitate understanding and resolution among students.	Merging – converging
On Table 1.1 under the indicator motivation with overall mean of 4.21, is rated as High, specifically in item number 2- being confident that I can effectively manage the stresses associated with adjusting to a new culture. (M= 4.10; High)	On Table 3.1, under the first category, Cultural Inclusivity and Respect core idea number 2- Teaching the students to respect one another by emphasizing the importance of respect in preventing conflicts.	Merging – converging
On Table 1.1 under the indicator knowledge with overall mean of 4.14, is rated as High, specifically in item number 5- seeking actively to understand the perspectives of individuals from other cultures rather than making assumptions based on my own cultural background. (M= 4.33; Very High)	On Table 3.1, under the second category, Practicing Fair Treatment core idea number 1- Being open-minded and accepting ideas from all students who show interest in participating in class.	Merging – converging
On Table 1.1 under the indicator motivation with overall mean of 4.21, is rated as High, specifically in item number 4- being open-minded and receptive to learning about new cultures and ways of life. (M= 4.40; Very High)	On Table 3.2, under the second category, Developing Cultural Intelligence core idea number 1 - Teacher should be open for new learnings, attend trainings and seminars that involve cultural intelligence.	Merging – converging

Using Cultural intelligence in Teaching. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the knowledge rated as high. This mean that it’s sometimes manifested by the teacher. in particular Item No. 2- Being knowledgeable about the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures got the mean of 4.11, which is rated as high. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which theme as embracing culture sensitive classroom under the second category adoption of culture responsive pedagogy. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this suggest that being knowledgeable about student’s diverse cultural values and religious beliefs help them enhance their teaching methods and promote inclusivity.

Moreover, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the Strategy rated as high. This mean that it is sometimes manifested by the teacher specifically in Item No. 1- Knowing what cultural knowledge I utilize when engaging with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds which got the highest mean of, which describe as very high. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is theme a fostering culture responsive teachings under the first category, practical implementation of cultural intelligence core idea - being essential in creating an inclusive learning environment, adopting teaching methods, and fostering mutual respect among students from diverse cultural backgrounds. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this highlights the idea of how important to be culturally intelligent in dealing individual from diverse cultural background and it help to promote inclusion and effective communication in the classroom.

Additionally, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the motivation rated as high. specifically in Item No. 5- Being adaptable and flexible when faced with unfamiliar cultural norms and practices (M= 4.22; High). The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which essential theme embracing culture sensitive classroom specifically in first category, adoption of culture responsive pedagogy, core idea- adapting to individual’s culture to understand their differences and have a culture-sensitive classroom. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this emphasizes that being adaptable and flexible in understanding the students’ unfamiliar cultural norms and practices enable them to create a culture-sensitive classroom wherein all students should be respected.

Further, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the behavior with overall mean of 4.19, is rated as High, specifically in Item No. 5- Changing my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires and needed it. (M= 4.33; Very High). The result is connected with the qualitative findings, under the second category, emerging language barriers core idea - having language barriers is a problem within the classroom and I adjusted my ways of teachings by using different methods. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this highlights the behavior that need to possess by a teacher in dealing individuals with diverse cultural background by adjusting their ways of interacting and teaching students using different methods and strategies.

Furthermore, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the strategy with overall mean of 4.38 rated as very high, specifically in

Item No. 3- Knowing the cultural knowledge I employ in cross-cultural interactions got the mean of 4.25 which rated as high. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, under the second category, establishing a welcoming learning environment core idea - employing active learning and cultural sensitivity counseling to facilitate understanding and resolution among students. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this highlights the idea of how teacher establish a welcoming learning environment by employing activate learning and cultural sensitivity in cross-cultural interaction to facilitate understanding and resolution.

Consequently, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the motivation with overall mean of 4.21, is rated as High, specifically in Item No. 2- Being confident that I can effectively manage the stresses associated with adjusting to a new culture which got a mean 4.10 rated as High. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which essential theme is strategies to address potential biases and stereotypes under the first category, cultural inclusivity and respect core idea - teaching the students to respect one another by emphasizing the importance of respect in preventing conflicts. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this indicates that private school teachers are confident to effectively manage stresses such as potential biases and conflict by teaching the students to respect one other and by that it can create inclusive environment.

Similarly, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the knowledge with overall mean of 4.14, is rated as High, specifically in Item No. 5- Seeking actively to understand the perspectives of individuals from other cultures rather than making assumptions based on my own cultural background got a mean 4.33 rated as very high. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which essential theme is strategies to address potential biases and under the second category, practicing fair treatment core idea- being open-minded and accepting ideas from all students who show interest in participating in class. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this indicates that private school teacher should understand the different perspective of the students with regarding with their cultural differences, teacher should possess fair treatment among students and be open to accept ideas and various perspectives from students and not being self-centered.

Lastly, In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the motivation with overall mean of 4.21, is rated as High, specifically in Item No. 4- Being open-minded and receptive to learning about new cultures and ways of life. (M= 4.40; Very High). The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which essential theme is enhancing teacher competence in cultural understanding under the second category, developing cultural intelligence core idea- teacher should be open for new learnings, attend trainings and seminars that involve cultural intelligence. Hence, the qualitative and quantitative correlate each other as this implies that in developing cultural intelligence it is crucial to be open-minded and receptive for new learnings, they can attend seminars and trainings that involve developing cultural intelligence.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the status of private school teacher's cultural intelligence is high in terms of knowledge, motivation, behavior and very high in terms of strategy. Hence, this indicate that the indicators of are always cultural intelligence manifested by the private school teachers.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based from the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI). The results gave more information about the side of the in terms of their experiences encountered in teaching a culturally diverse classroom and enhancing their cultural intelligence. Qualitatively, private school teachers have been experiencing different situations which contribute to the way their cultural intelligence is being use in teaching. The study revealed several key themes: embracing culturally sensitive classrooms, overcoming cultural hindrances and language barriers, navigating challenges related to cultural differences, and developing strategies to address potential biases and stereotypes.

Third, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the insight shared of private school teachers regarding challenges faced in developing cultural intelligence in their professional academic work. The study identified the following key themes: fostering culturally responsive teaching, enhancing teacher competence in cultural understanding, fostering cultural sensitivity and inclusive education, and including culture in the curriculum.

Lastly, a thematic analysis of the responses was conducted to validate the study's quantitative findings and gain a deeper understanding of how teachers' experiences contribute to the development of cultural intelligence. The nature plan is used to incorporate the results from the two phases. The data obtained from the qualitative phase converged with the state of cultural intelligence as determined by the quantitative results. It is confirmed by both the quantitative and qualitative results that teaching children from diverse cultural backgrounds can be beneficial when cultural intelligence is incorporated into the curriculum. Teachers may establish a welcoming classroom that values equality, respect, and inclusivity by using cultural knowledge.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the status of the cultural intelligence reveal that among the four indicators of cultural intelligence, the knowledge has the lowest mean which affects how teacher use cultural intelligence in teaching culturally diverse students, it is recommend that teacher may continuously utilize and incorporate their cultural knowledge in their lessons to develop and enhance their cultural intelligence. Enhancing teachers' knowledge of cultural intelligence emphasized professional development that deepen teachers understanding of

cultural nuances within the classroom. By that they can create an environment that values cultural competence and encourages continuous learning.

Moreover, based from the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of private school teacher with regards to their cultural intelligence in teaching their students from diverse cultural background, teacher may look for new methods on how they can incorporate cultural intelligence into their teaching strategies more effectively. It is also, crucial to diversify professional development with targeted training on cultural awareness and effective interaction in diverse classroom. By integrating culturally responsive pedagogy it can provide a continuous learning opportunity, and advocate for inclusive school policies that celebrate diversity.

Furthermore, insight shared of private school teacher with regards in integration of cultural intelligence in their academic professional work may use to meet the learning needs of the diverse students. teacher should engage in ongoing self-reflection and seek opportunities for development. Also, new strategies may form by adapting instructional materials and teaching methods that honor and reflect the cultural background of their students. By continually deepening their understanding of cultural nuances and striving to create inclusive environments, teachers can effectively leverage cultural intelligence in their professional academic work.

Lastly, it is also being recommended for the teacher too actively engage with diverse cultural resources and perspectives outside the classroom. This could involve attending some cultural events, exploring literature and media from different cultures, or participating in community activities that celebrates diversity. By immersing themselves in various cultural experiences, teacher can broaden their understanding and appreciation of different cultures, which in turn enhances their cultural intelligence and enriches teaching strategies.

References

- Afsar, B. (2021). Cultural intelligence and innovative work behavior: the role of work engagement and interpersonal trust. Murdoch.edu.au. <https://researchportal.murdoch.edu.au/esploro/outputs/journalArticle/Cultural-intelligence-and-innovative-work-behavior/991005540592407891>
- Alev, S., & Kara, M. (2021). The Relationship between Cultural Intelligence and the Attitudes towards Refugee Students: A Study on Primary School Teacher. *Participatory Educational Research*, 8(1), 109–122. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=cultural+intelligence+strategy+teacher&ft=on&id=EJ1277154>
- Alexandra, V. (2022). Optimizing cultural intelligence development by considering different types of change. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2022.2081060>
- Alifuddin, M., & Widodo, W. (2022). How Is Cultural Intelligence Related to Human Behavior? *Journal of Intelligence*, 10. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=cultural+intelligence+strategy+teacher&ft=on&id=EJ1353696>
- Ang, M. (2018, October). PHILIPPINES: A FRAMEWORK TO DEVELOP INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE FOR GLOBAL EDUCATION <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328276686>
- Ang, S., & Van Dyne, L. (2007). Cultural Intelligence: Its Measurement and Effects on Cultural Judgment and Decision Making, Cultural Adaptation and Task Performance. *Management and Organization Review*, 3(3), 335–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-8784.2007.00082.x>
- Ashley, M. (2020a). Cultural Intelligence and Its Relationship to Leadership Effectiveness in Independent Private Schools - ProQuest. www.proquest.com. <https://search.proquest.com/openview/0cea9502d5d5fb9265b1e92aa254d07f/1?pq>
- Aziz, J. (2024). Fostering a Culturally Responsive Pedagogy through Teacher's Discourse: A Case of Graduate Class at a U.S. University. ERIC. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Overcoming+Cultural+Hindrances+and+Language+Barriers+in+culturally+diverse+>
- Bennett, M. (2017). Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318430742_Developmental_Model_of_Intercultural_Sensitivity
- Bjarnason, N. (2023). Creating a Culturally Responsive Classroom for World Language Classes: A Connection of CRT and Comprehensible Input, a Study of Strategies and Best Practices.
- Borden, C. (n.d.). Subject Guides: International Education: Cultural Competence. <https://subjectguides.nsc.ca/internationaleducation/Culturalcompetence>
- Bricki, N. and Green, J. (2007) A Guide to Using Qualitative Research Methodology. – References Scientific Research Publishing. (2021). <https://www.scirp.org/%28S%28cez2tfqyw2orz553k1w0r45%29%>
- Brislin, R. (2019). Cultural Intelligence: Understanding Behaviors that Serve People's Goals. *Group & Organization Management*, 31(1), 40–55. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601105275262>
- Bryman, A. (2007). Barriers to Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1, Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.). www.scirp.org. [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje\)\)/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=1266482](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje))/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=1266482)

- Creswell, J.W. (2013) *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Scientific Research Publishing. (2013). Scirp.org. [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje\)\)/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=1485543](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje))/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=1485543)
- Dawadi, S., Shrestha, S., & Giri, R. A. (2021). Mixed-Methods Research: a Discussion on Its Types, Challenges, and Criticisms. *Journal of Practical Studies in Education*, 2(2), 25–36. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED611786.pdf>
- Demir, S. B., & Pismek, N. (2018). A Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Study of Controversial Issues in Social Studies Classes: a Clash of Ideologies. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2018.1.0298>
- Didem, A. (2020). Cultural Intelligence Levels of Pre-Service Teachers. *Journal of Education and New Approaches*, 2020(1), 50–65. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1170350>
- Dolzhenko, I., & Young, J. (2020). Understanding Teachers' Cultural Competencies: Supporting the Development of Teachers' Self-Awareness and Social Awareness. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338299540_Understanding_Teachers'_Cultural_Competencies_Supporting_the_Development_of_Teachers'_Self-Awareness_and_Social_Awareness
- Donahue, C. (2022). In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Master of Arts in Education. <https://scholarworks.calstate.edu/downloads/s7526j76r?locale=en>
- Gokalp, S. (2022). The Relationship between School Principals' Cultural Intelligence Level and Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Intention to Leave the Job. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 11(1), 493–509. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=cultural+intelligence+strategy+teacher&ft=on&id=EJ1329214>
- Groenewald, T. (2004) *A Phenomenological Research Design Illustrated*. International Journal of Qualitative Methods, - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.).
- Halawi, L. (2023). Harnessing the Power of Culture and Cultural Intelligence within Knowledge Management Systems. In *www.intechopen.com*. IntechOpen. <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/1145346>
- Hepler, R. (2023). Multicultural Education | Definition, Methods & Examples. *study.com*. <https://study.com/learn/lesson/multicultural-education-overview-approaches.html#:~:text=The%20different%20multicultural%20approaches%20to,hero%20archetype%20of>
- Idrus, F., & Sohid, M. (2023). Teachers' Expectations and Challenges in Using Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT) Strategies in the ESL Classroom. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 14(3), 629–635. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1403.10>
- Kaya, M. M. (2022). Teaching Locally, Acting Globally: The Effect of Pre-Service Teachers' Cultural Intelligence Levels on Their Perceptions of Global Citizens. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 18(4), 132–147. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=cultural+intelligence+strategy+teacher&ft=on&id=EJ1352247>
- Kedzior, J. (n.d.). Self-Reported Multicultural Teaching Knowledge and Skills of Self-Reported Multicultural Teaching Knowledge and Skills of School <https://thekeep.eiu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=5884&context=theses>
- Latha, B. V. (2023). THE ROLE OF CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENHANCING CROSS-CULTURAL BUSINESS RELATIONSHIPS: AN ANALYSIS. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2308221.pdf>
- Lehman, C. (n.d.). ScholarWorks Multicultural Competence for Teaching Diverse Students as Experienced by Preservice Teachers. from <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3263&context=dissertations>
- Li, J., Wu, N., & Xiong, S. (2021). Sustainable innovation in the context of organizational cultural diversity: The role of cultural intelligence and knowledge sharing. *PLOS ONE*, 16(5), e0250878. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0250878>
- Miller, C. (2020). Intercultural Communication Competence. *Cod.pressbooks.pub*. <https://cod.pressbooks.pub/communication/chapter/8-4-intercultural-communication-competence/>
- Miller, W. E. (1976). The Less Obvious Functions of Archiving Survey Research Data. *American Behavioral Scientist*. https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Cross-Cultural+Approaches+to+Measuring+Motivation&ft=on&ff1=dytSince_2019&id=EJ136906
- Moore, S. (2021, June 10). Cultural Competence in Education. *TeachHUB*. <https://www.teachhub.com/professional-development/2021/06/cultural-competence-in-education/>
- Muñiz, J. (2020). Culturally Responsive Teaching: A Reflection Guide. In ERIC. *New America*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED609136>
- Myrna F. Dagohoy. (2019). THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS. *Southeast Asian Journal of Educational Management*, 1(1), 1–1.
- Paiuc, D. (2021). The Impact of Cultural Intelligence on Multinational Leadership: A Semantic Review. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge Economy*, 9(1), 81–93. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=943521>

- Pettigrew, T. F. (1998). (PDF) Intergroup Contact Theory. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5282610_Intergroup_Contact_Theory
- Pogosyan, M. (2022, June 29). The What, How and Why of Cultural Intelligence. Psychology Today. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/between-cultures/202206/the-what-how-and-why-cultural-intelligence>
- Rajaram, K. (2023). Cultural Intelligence in Teaching and Learning. Learning Intelligence: Innovative and Digital Transformative Learning Strategies, 57–118. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-9201-8_2
- Rasmussen, L. (2018, October 12). Cross-Cultural Competence: Engage People from any Culture - Global Cognition. Global Cognition. <https://www.globalcognition.org/cross-cultural-competence/>
- Samuels, (2018). How to Embrace Culturally Responsive Teaching and Promote Student Success. Www.linkedin.com. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-embrace-culturally-responsive-teaching->
- Samuels, A. (2018). Exploring culturally responsive pedagogy: Teachers' perspectives on fostering equitable and inclusive classrooms. In SRATE Journal (Vol. 27, Issue 1, pp. 22–30). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1166706.pdf>
- Sanson, A., & Bretherton, D. (2007). CONFLICT RESOLUTION: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES. <https://bpb-us-w2.wpmucdn.com/u.osu.edu/dist/b/7538/files/2014/10/Chapter-17-Conflict-Resolution-Sanson-Bretherton-1myb0rn.pdf>
- Sarkar, D. I. (2024). Bridging Cultural Gaps: A Study of Cultural Intelligence in the Formation of Teacher Identity in Hyderabad. Journal of Engineering Education Transformations, 37(Special Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.16920/jeet/2024/v37is2/24128>
- Seeberg, V., & Minick, T. (2012). Enhancing Cross-cultural Competence in Multicultural Teacher Education: Transformation in Global Learning. International Journal of Multicultural Education, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.18251/ijme.v14i3.56>
- Stoermer, S., Davies, S., & Froese, F. J. (2020). The influence of expatriate cultural intelligence on organizational embeddedness and knowledge sharing: The moderating effects of host country context. Journal of International Business Studies
- Suharli, S. (2020). The Implementation of Social Studies Learning Model Based on Cultural Intelligence. Atlantis Press. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/125957034.pdf>
- Syzenko, A., & Diachkova, Y. (2020). Building Cross-Cultural Competence in a Foreign Language through Technology-Enhanced Project-Based Learning. Revista Amazonia Investiga, 9(27), 411–418. <https://doi.org/10.34069/ai/2020.27.03.45>
- Urhahne, D., & Wijnia, L. (2023). Theories of Motivation in Education: an Integrative Framework. Educational Psychology <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09767-9>
- Van Dyne, L., & Koh, C. (2012). Sub-Dimensions of the Four Factor Model of Cultural Intelligence: Expanding the Conceptualization and Measurement of Cultural Intelligence. Social and Personality Psychology Compass, 6(4), 295–313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2012.00429.x>
- Vargas-Bello-Pérez, E., & Hernández-Castellano, L. E. (2019). Practical and innovative solutions to overcome language barriers in veterinary and animal science education in the European Union. Journal of Applied Animal Research, 47(1), 429–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09712119.2019.1651728>
- Villagran, M. A. L. (2022). Cultural Competence in Research. School of Information Student Research Journal, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.31979/2575-2499.120103>
- Yang, C. (2023). Motivational cultural intelligence and well-being in cross-cultural workplaces: a study of migrant workers in Taiwan. VLex. <https://vlex.co.uk/vid/motivational-cultural-intelligence-and-940189452>
- Yenpech, C., & Intanoo, K. (2022). Intercultural Sensitivity and Social Intelligence: The Case of EFL Internship Undergraduate Learners. Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies, 18(2), 860–876. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=cultural+intelligence+strategy+teacher&ft=on&id=EJ1347328>
- Zamroni, Dwiningrum, S. I. A., Hope, J., Kartowagiran, B., Sudartinah, T., Siteine, A., & Yao, Z. (2021). Cross-Cultural Competence in Multicultural Education

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Wendilyn A. Balinon

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines